

was established in 2015 as a 'knowledge and innovation community' (KIC) with focus on health and aging. EIT Health is a vast, strong, and diverse European network of best-in-class organisations across education, research, industry, and healthcare delivery, which work across borders with partners, start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and entrepreneurs to answer the biggest healthcare challenges.

EIT Health goals:

- **Strengthening Healthcare Systems in Europe:** to overcome obstacles to innovation to improve healthcare delivery in Europe and make life-changing solutions possible. The goal is to remove barriers across borders to create a more resilient and dynamic European healthcare system.
- **Promoting Better Health of Citizens:** to raise awareness, share knowledge and create the tools, treatment and breakthrough solutions which will promote healthy living and active ageing.
- **Contributing to a Sustainable Health Economy in Europe:** to create a fertile environment in which innovation can flourish. By building health enterprises and bringing innovative products and services to market, the goal is to create new jobs to grow and strengthen a sustainable European economy.

EIT Health Flagships:

- **New Models to Deliver Healthcare (NMDH):** this Flagship aims to support the delivery of new models to deliver healthcare utilising evidence-based approaches leveraged by robust analysis of patient experiences, as well as clinical and economic data. The Flagship is focusing on the concept of value-based healthcare, where success is measured through patients' outcomes and the shift of healthcare from treatment to prevention. Specific activities are:

- **EIT Health Innovation Day Series (i-Days)**: host a challenge-based learning event that trains participants in innovation and entrepreneurship, design thinking methods, and pitching,
 - **Modules Towards a Labelled Fellowship Programme**: deliver personalised online learning pathways that teach theoretical and practical skills or knowledge to apply in a professional environment,
 - **Service Development Activity**: collaborate on activities that promote the market uptake of innovative products and services by assessing the quality of the healthcare service improvement.
- **Digital Transformation of Healthcare (DTH)**: this Flagship aims to support the digital health transformation in Europe and will focus on the development of, and access to, **digital medical devices**. It will also support the implementation of the European Health Data Space through exploring the secondary use of **data**. It will finally focus on how patients, citizens, and healthcare professionals are trained to understand the importance and relevance of data sharing in informing and improving the continuum of care pathways. Specific activities are:
 - **EIT Health Innovation Day Series (i-Days)**: host a challenge-based learning event that trains participants in innovation and entrepreneurship, design thinking methods, and pitching,
 - **Master Degree Programme**: if you are Higher Education Institution, you can join a consortium led by EIT Health, with the goal of incorporating entrepreneurship and innovation education elements into their existing master's programmes,
 - **Modules Towards a Labelled Fellowship Programme**: deliver personalised online learning pathways that teach theoretical and practical skills or knowledge to apply in a professional environment,
 - **Modules Towards EIT Labelled Certification**: provide high-quality content that feeds into modules on the EIT Health Academy,
 - **Technology Development Activity**: for collaborative SMEs or industry led projects that focus on validation, certification, and market access of patient-centred DMD solutions in Europe to facilitate market entry and wider adoption,
 - **DiGinnovation Programme**: if you are a top digital health micro and small enterprise, we link you with international entities to create a consortium that will improve healthcare systems.
- **The Re-industrialisation of Europe**: the IPCEI Flagship, initially channelled through the so-called European Initiative in Health, led by 16 Member States and supported by the European Commission, will be extended to a wider topic called "The Re-Industrialisation of Europe". This Flagship aims at addressing the dual imperative of:

- equipping Europe with a **strong, innovative, and export-friendly healthcare industry** that can meet the challenges posed by the future of medical care and,
- developing **lasting and innovative European manufacturing capabilities regarding critical products, notably pharmaceuticals.**

This Flagship will have a dedicated call for activities.

New Models to Deliver Healthcare

Digital Transformation of Healthcare

The Re-industrialisation of Europe

Source: <https://eithealth.eu/>

EIT Health partnership model:

Type of partnership	Annual membership fees	Funding
Premium (Core) Partner	€65,000 membership fee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unlimited amount of EIT financial support • can involve an unlimited number of their Affiliated entities
Associate Partner	€25,000 membership fee and 5% management fee on the amount of financial support received	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unlimited amount of EIT financial support • can involve an unlimited number of their Affiliated entities, however a €5,000 fee is applied for each active Affiliated Entity
External Partner	No membership fee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-members of the association

	<p>10% management fee on EIT financial support received</p> <p>SMEs:</p> <p>Medium enterprises: €10,000 membership fee and 5% management fee on the amount of financial support received</p> <p>Micro/Small companies: €1,000 membership fee and 5% management fee on the amount of financial support received</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • can propose and participate in activities • participation is limited to €50,000 of EIT financial support per financial year • if a Micro/Small company is acting as the commercialising entity in a Technology or Service development activities and has chosen the Grant for Options financial sustainability model, it is exempt from paying the management fee
Network Partner	Between €1,000 and €5,000 for the services provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • represent the user community that enable the implementation of EIT Health activities and innovations • include municipalities, patient organizations and financiers such as business angels groups and venture capital companies,

		<p>incubators, regional clusters, local accelerators, test bed hospitals...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • directly associated with one of Co-location Centres • if a Network Partner successfully applies to the Flagship Call, the same rules of participation as for External Partners will apply
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EIT Health Flagships Call 2024:

Flagship	Activities*
New models to deliver healthcare	<p>EIT Health Innovation Days Series (i-Days)</p> <p>Modules towards a Labelled Fellowship Programme</p> <p>Service Development activity</p>
Digital Transformation of Healthcare	<p>EIT Health Innovation Days Series (i-Days)</p> <p>Master Degree Programme</p> <p>Modules towards EIT Labelled Certification</p> <p>Modules towards a Labelled Fellowship Programme</p> <p>Technology development activity</p> <p>DiGinnovation programme</p>

* In pink: Technology and Service Development activities, in green: Education-related programmes

Application deadline: **28 February 2024** and **18 September 2024** depending on the proposal type. The cut-off dates are the deadlines for short proposals and/or single proposal submission. It is important to note that not all activities called within the Flagship framework will be called at both cut-offs.

More information: <https://eithealth.eu/programmes/flagship-hub/>

EIT Health programmes:

are unique offerings that give the opportunity to learn new skills, connect with a vast network of experts, access new markets and finance and more.

More information: <https://eithealth.eu/what-we-do/our-programmes/>

More information about EIT Health: <https://eithealth.eu/>

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